

Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-*p*-N-Dimethylaminoaniline Complexes with Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+}

M. S. MAYADEO and V. P. DHAKAPPA

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay-400 019

Manuscript received 21 January 1979, revised 29 January 1980, accepted 19 May 1980

Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} , with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*p*-N-dimethylaminoaniline. The dissociation constants (pK_a and pK_b) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1M in 75 : 25 per cent (v/v) dioxan-water medium. The order of stability constants of the chelates is found to be $\text{Dy}^{3+} > \text{Pr}^{3+} > \text{Gd}^{3+} > \text{Nd}^{3+}$. The validity of Born's relation was examined by studying the plot of Z^2/r vs $\log K$ values of the rare earth complexes of the ligand.

IN the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*p*-N-dimethylaminoaniline with various trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum *pH* titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The Corning Model 12, a precision research *pH* meter with a combined glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for *pH* measurements. Both electrodes dip into the titration mixture, without vitiating any of the results. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. The changes in *pH* can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 *pH* unit.

Experimental

The ligand, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*p*-N-dimethylaminoaniline was prepared by dissolving 10 gm of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) in 50 ml of absolute ethanol. To this was added equimolar quantity of *p*-N-dimethylaminoaniline and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for half an hour. After cooling, the solution was filtered to get the crude product, which was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to get analytically pure compound with m.p. 168° (observed). The structural formula of the ligand is—

The dioxan used for experimental work was purified by the method described by Vogel².

Distilled water redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate was used throughout the investigation.

The medium of titration was 75 : 25 per cent dioxan-water (v/v) mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling the oxygen free nitrogen gas through the solutions. The free acid, the free acid plus the ligand and the mixture of metal ion containing the acid plus the ligand were titrated against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide. The solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared using metal carbonate of pure quality (Fluka) and A. R. grade perchloric acid. All these were standardised complexometrically³ by EDTA titrations. All measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.025 M), solution.

(i) 5 ml of (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml of dioxan.

(ii) 5 ml of (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

(iii) 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml of metal perchlorate (0.008 M) in (0.16 M) HClO_4 + the requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

The data obtained from above titrations are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*p*-N-dimethylaminoaniline.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test the reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be stated here that the reagent does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after one hour. This has also been confirmed by T.L.C. taken from time to time of a sample titration mixture.

In the ligand it is the phenolic (OH) group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y', the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1) using the solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_A values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated and a curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted. The formation curve extends over a range

$0.15 < \bar{n}_A < 1.8$ and is wavelike. The value of pK_1^H which corresponds to phenolic 'H' was evaluated from the half-integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ while that of pK_2^H which corresponds to the association of protonated nitrogen was obtained at $\bar{n}_A = 1.5$.

The formation of LH corresponds to the reaction

while the reaction leading to the formation of LH_2^+ can be

The protonation of the nitrogen of $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ (imino nitrogen) does not take place in the range of pH under study as this nitrogen is less basic as

compared to the nitrogen of $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ group.

The plots of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right]$ vs B and $\log \left[\frac{(2 - \bar{n}_A)}{(\bar{n}_A - 1)} \right]$ against B were also drawn. From the former pK_1^H was evaluated and from the latter pK_2^H was evaluated. The values agree quite well with those obtained by the half-integral method.

From the titration curves using solutions (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria (Fig. 2). From these formation curves, the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ were calculated which correspond to pL values at

$\bar{n} = 0.5$. The plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}}{(1 - \bar{n})} \right]$ against pL was also drawn for these systems. The values of $\log K_1$ evaluated from these plots agree quite well with those obtained by half-integral method.

Fig. 2. Metal ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-*p*-N-dimethylaminoaniline.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability of the trivalent metal chelates was found to be $Dy^{3+} > Pr^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Nd^{3+}$.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

Cations	$t = 25^\circ C$				
	H^+	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}
$\log K_1$	9.32	6.82	6.48	6.63	9.02
$\log K_2$	5.37	—	—	—	—

* For proton association (H^+), K_1 and K_2 corresponds to the species LH and LH_2^+ respectively, while for metal ions K_1 corresponds to the species ML_1 .

The second step formation constants for metal chelates could not be evaluated because of precipitation of metal ions probably due to metal ion hydrolysis.

Rare earths normally form ionic compounds. The possibility of covalent interaction, however,

cannot be completely excluded as reported in the case of acetylacetonone chelates of rare earths⁴.

If the bonds are ionic, the Born relation $E = Z^2/2r(1 - \frac{1}{D})$ should hold for the energy change on complexation of a gaseous ion of charge 'Z' and radius 'r' in a medium of dielectric constant 'D'. Since the stability constant is related directly to this energy, the $\log K$ values should increase linearly with Z^2/r .

The plots of Z^2/r vs $\log K_1$ values of the rare earth complexes do not exhibit any linear increase of $\log K_1$ with increase in Z^2/r . The probable explanation of non-linearity could be that the assumption about ionic character of metal-ligand bond on which the linear relation is based is not valid. The other probable causes are (i) coordination number of metal ion greater than six, and (ii) steric factor.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay, for the valuable suggestions and to Dr. R. A. Kulkarni, Principal, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay, for his kind and continuous encouragement in accomplishing this work.

References

1. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
2. A. I. VOGEL, *A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry*, III Edition, Longmans, p. 177.
3. H. A. FLASCHKA, 'EDTA Titrations', Pergamon Press, N. Y., p. 73.
4. T. D. MOELLER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 1.